

Increasing Student Learning Interest in the Subject "Indonesia in the Period of Independence" through the STAD Method (Student Teams Achievement Division)

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study was to improve learning achievement using the Student Teams Achievement Division (STAD) method, at SMP Negeri 2 Muntilan, Magelang, which is located at Jalan Wates Muntilan KP 56417 (0293) 587567, Muntilan, Magelang, Central Java. The object of this study were 9 D grade students, 2022/2023 academic year, with a total of 30 students, consisting of 18 girls and 12 boys. The research process or learning improvement is carried out in 2 cycles. Cycle I was held on Thursday, 19 October 2022 and cycle II was held on Thursday, 9 November 2022. Each cycle consists of 4 stages, namely: (1) Planning (Plan), (2) Implementation of Action (Action), (3) Observation (Observation), and (4) Reflection (Reflection). The results of the study concluded that the use of the student's team achievement division method can improve learning activities and learning outcomes in students in grade 9 D, Muntilan 1 Public Middle School, Magelang, Central Java. The results of the research in Cycle I that reached KKM/*Kriteria Ketuntasan Minimal*/ Minimum Completeness Criteria (70) were 4 students or 1.2% of 30 students. In cycle II, 27 students achieved KKM (70) or in other words, reached 90%. Thus it has increased by 90%. The results of the classroom action research above imply that by using the students teams achievement division method not only do students want to learn academic skills and content, but also learn to understand several aspects of life, especially in collaborating or working together to advance or achieve all.

KEYWORDS: KKM (*Kriteria Ketuntasan Minimal*/ Minimum Completeness Criteria; Student Team Achievement Division (STAD); social science; learning achievement

I. INTRODUCTION

Social Sciences (IPS) subjects are one of the subjects taught at the junior high school (SMP) level of education. Social studies learning carried out in this junior high school should be able to foster students' logical, critical, systematic, motivational, and creative attitudes towards the mastery of the social studies field that occurs in their environment. It is intended that students are able to analyze what they learn, examine, and be thorough in making decisions, and be able to reason about the relationship of historical events, which are associated with one event with other events so as to be able to create a scientific mindset. Critical early on.

This scientific attitude and perspective occurs when students are actively (fully) involved in ongoing learning. IPS learning that is designed, challenging, motivating, and at the same time interesting, not only knowledge in the form of facts, concepts, and theories, which are simply given to students, but more than that is planning how the learning should be meaningful, challenging, and stimulating students' curiosity. Students are expected to be able to demonstrate a logical, systematic, critical, and creative attitude.

However, the experience of researchers who are also teachers, especially in grade 9 semesters I and II of SMP Negeri 2 Muntilan, Magelang, regarding social studies material on the subject "Indonesia's Independence Period" and its influence in daily life, shows something to be wary of. The scores obtained by students are still below the KKM (although not all of them). Based on the results of the pre-cycle evaluation in class 9 D, SMP Negeri 2 Muntilan, 90% of students had not met the KKM in a class of 30 students. This means that it can be categorized that learning is not good. The KKM for social studies class 9 for the 2022/2023 academic year is 70. After tracing the low learning achievement, it is caused by several factors, namely factors from students and teachers. Factors from students, namely students showing less interest in Social Sciences (IPS) learning material because they are

Increasing Student Learning Interest in the Subject "Indonesia in the Period of Independence" through the STAD Method (Student Teams Achievement Division)

not interested in the concepts being taught so students are less motivated. The learning process becomes stagnant, students' understanding is serious, their sympathy for social studies subjects is lacking, the literacy they acquire is also lacking, at the same time the anticipation of these problems is not optimal and it can even be said that handling is still slow.

Meanwhile, the factors from the teacher, namely the teacher too often uses the lecture and question and answer method only so that students do not understand the concept well, the students' memory does not last long, learning motivation is still low, tips and tricks for solving difficult problems are still less than expected. the effect is that students are less able to memorize the lessons that have been given by their teacher.

This kind of condition is a challenge for researchers as class 9 D teachers, Muntilan 2 Public Junior High School. An active (*Pembelajaran aktif*), innovative (*inovatif*), creative (*kreatif*), effective (*efektif*), fun (*menyenangkan*), enthusiastic (*antusias*), optimistic (*optimis*), conducive (*kondusif*), happy (*gembira*), and meaningful learning (*berbobot*) model (PAIKEM SEMOK GEMBROT) is a demand that must be answered (Budiyono and Ngumarno: 2021; Budiyono: 2021; Magdalena, I et al. : 2020). Researchers are required to be able to answer all kinds of challenges in the study. Therefore a solution is needed that is able to overcome and improve the conditions and abilities of grade 9 D of SMP Negeri 2 Muntilan in understanding Social Science material with the subject "Indonesia During the Independence Period".

Based on the above, according to the researcher's opinion, a reliable learning method is an alternative that can increase understanding of mastery of material related to our country, Indonesia, during the period of preparation for independence. The application of the Student Teams Achievement Division (STAD) learning method is one method that is quite well applied in this class. The learning process takes place by the teacher directing the implementation plan first, then forming small groups (consisting of 4 to 5 people) per group, then there is one person as the group leader, which they finally discuss together to solve the problems they face. Students prepare questions and answers related to the problems they face/difficult for them (Budiyono, et al: 2018; 2019a; 2019b; 2021;). With this step, students can be motivated and gain experience from this method and not just lectures, as well as questions and answers from the teacher. That is what underlies the researcher to raise this problem in this classroom action research.

II. METHOD

The subjects of the study were 30 students at Public Junior High School 2 Muntilan, Magelang, Central Java for the 2022/2023 academic year, consisting of 12 boys and 18 girls. The following tabel describes the number of students who were used as research material.

Table 1. List of Class 9 D SMP Negeri 2 Muntilan

No	Student Identification Number	Name of Student	Gender
1	6547	Adi Nugroho	M
2	6515	Agung Hendrawan Widiyanto	M
3	6453	Aisyah Nur Janah	F
4	6516	Akhmad Syifa Fawaid	M
5	6454	Alika Az Zahra	F
6	6582	Annisaa Nur Aeni	F
7	6584	Ayu Wandira	F
8	6493	Chalista Larasati Kusuma	F
9	6463	Dewi Sri Bandiyah	F
10	6497	Eisha Aulia Ramadani	F
11	6551	Fadli Imam Muttaqin	M
12	6589	Fardhan Yusuf Darmawan	M
13	6590	Faris Rizq Ardiansyah	M
14	6465	Febrianla Ahnaf Aufa Kurniawan	M
15	6594	Kirana Ajwa Prameswari	F
16	6472	Muhammad Raffi Pratama	M
17	6627	Muhammad Rafi Khairi	M
18	6598	Naf'an Fikri Nasoha	M
19	6629	Nailun Ni'mah	F
20	6559	Naura Kirania Hermawan	F
21	6603	Niken Ayu Sekar Wigati	F
22	6563	Putri Nuril Lailatul Hidayah	F
23	6631	Ragil Rizqi Yanuar	M
24	6478	Reni Fadhillah Izzana	F
25	6636	Satrio Cahyo Wicaksono	M
26	6607	Silvi Nur Fadhila	F
27	6572	Silvia Novita Ningrum	F
28	6512	Siti 'Ainunna'imah	F

Increasing Student Learning Interest in the Subject "Indonesia in the Period of Independence" through the STAD Method (Student Teams Achievement Division)

29	6577	Wulan Amelia	F
30	6514	Yasmien Putri Hapsari	F

F : Female

M: Male

The implementation of learning improvement is carried out at Muntilan 2 Public Middle School, Jalan Wates Muntilan, Magelang, Central Java, KP 56415 Telephone (0293) 587567. Meanwhile the subject matter that is targeted is Social Sciences, the sub-topic of "Indonesia's Independence Period - Reformation" for grade 9 D semester II 2022/2023 Academic Year.

The research time was carried out in two cycles of learning improvement with the following time divisions. a). Cycle I was held on Thursday, 19 October 2022, 09.00 – 10.10 WIB; b). Cycle II was held on Thursday, November 9 2022, 09.00 – 10.10 WIB.

In carrying out the improvement of learning researchers are assisted by several parties, namely: a. Yulianto, M.Pd., as Plt. Principal at SMP Negeri 2; Muntilan, Jl. Wates Muntilan, KP 56415 Tel. (0293) 587567; who have given permission and provided guidance to the author; b. Dr. Sri Budiyo, M.Pd. as Supervisor I, who has been willing to take the time to provide guidance and direction in a patient and full of wisdom in the Improvement of Learning and the preparation of this report; c. Andhyka Murti, M. Pd., Supervisor II who has also taken the time to provide guidance and direction patiently and wisely in Learning Improvement and preparation of this report; d. Harisah Rachmawati, S.Pd. as Peer Partner I in implementing improvements and as teachers, who are both striving to improve student achievement; e. Sugiwarni, S.Pd.Ek., as Partner 2 in the implementation of repairs and as a teacher, who never gets tired of being invited to discuss solving problems that we both face, as well as sharing opinions in choosing ways and efforts to improve student achievement; f. Grade 9 students of SMP Negeri 2 Muntilan who are willing to provide information and at the same time take tests for this classroom action research.

The researcher analyzed the data from the results of the assessment used to find out how far the Student Teams Achievement Division (STAD) method can improve student achievement. Quantitative data is in the form of students' daily test result

Results = total score x 5 = 100

$$M = \frac{\sum \text{value score}}{n \text{ student}}$$

Calculating percentages $P = f/N \times 100 \%$

The researcher analyzed the data in a comparative descriptive manner through observation to compare the initial conditions with the data obtained from the research data. Data on learning outcomes, in the form of scores obtained by students from the tests given, were then analyzed quantitatively. Meanwhile, observer comments on teacher performance in learning were analyzed descriptively qualitatively.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1 Description of Learning Improvement Research Results Pracyclus

In the following, learning improvement research is presented which is taken from the results of the scores before the improvement. This event was made with the intention to find out the results of the research before being treated with learning improvements. The description of research results prior to learning improvement is as follows below (see table 2).

Table 2. The Value of Student Achievement 9 D at The Pre-cycle Stage

No	Name	Score	Information
1	Adi Nugroho	35	H
2	Agung Hendrawan Widiyanto	37,5	H
3	Aisyah Nur Janah	40	H
4	Akhmad Syifa Fawaid	35	H
5	Alika Az Zahra	27,5	H
6	Annisaa Nur Aeni	30	H
7	Ayu Wandira	37,5	H
8	Chalista Larasati Kusuma	30	H
9	Dewi Sri Bandiyah	45	H
10	Eisha Aulia Ramadani	47,5	H
11	Fadli Imam Muttaqin	75	P
12	Fardhan Yusuf Darmawan	50	H
13	Faris Rizq Ardiansyah	50	H
14	Febrianla Ahnaf Aufa Kurniawan	27,5	H
15	Kirana Ajwa Prameswari	37,5	H
16	Muhammad Raffi Pratama	35	H
17	Muhammad Rafi Khairi	50	H
18	Naf'an Fikri Nasoha	35	H

Increasing Student Learning Interest in the Subject "Indonesia in the Period of Independence" through the STAD Method (Student Teams Achievement Division)

19	Nailun Ni'mah	42,5	H
20	Naura Kirania Hermawan	32,5	H
21	Niken Ayu Sekar Wigati	50	H
22	Putri Nurriil Lailatul Hidayah	42,5	H
23	Ragil Rizqi Yanuar	52,5	H
24	Reni Fadhilah Izzana	47,5	H
25	Satrio Cahyo Wicaksono	27,5	H
26	Silvi Nur Fadhila	22,5	H
27	Silvia Novita Ningrum	52,5	H
28	Siti 'Ainunna'Imah	52,5	H
29	Wulan Amelia	47,5	H
30	Yasmien Putri Hapsari	77,5	P
T o t a l		1.272,5	
Average Score		30	

Information: H = haven't passed yet (Still not passed the standard minimum completeness criteria)

P = Passed (Has passed the standard minimum completeness criteria)

From the data above it can be seen that of the 30 students there were 2 students who received a score of 70. Meanwhile, out of the 30 students, 28 others did not fulfill or in other words did not complete because they were still far below the KKM (Minimum Completeness Criteria). There were 28 students who scored 70 out of 30 students. The impact is that if the average is taken, each student's student gets a score of 30. So, on average, it is still far below the KKM. The above data when classified as follows.

Classification A is a group of students who score 80-100 (zero). Classification B is a group of students who get a score of 70 – 79 which results in only two students namely on behalf of: Fadli Imam Muttaqin and Yasmien Putri Hapsari. Classification C: is a group of students who get a score of 60 – 69 which is equivalent to a C grade (enough). The result is nil, in the sense that not a single student gets a C grade (enough/only passes).

Classification D is a group of students who score less than 60. From the available data, some of them score below the KKM (Minimum Completeness Criteria). The results of previous learning improvement efforts were required using the students teams achievement division method, which can be seen in table 3 below.

Table 3. Recapitulation of Classification of Values and Percentage of Social Science Values Prior to Improvement in Grade 9 D Students, Muntilan 2 Public Middle School, Central Java

No	Classification	The Number of Students	Percentage	Completeness
1	A	-	-	-
2	B	2	2%	P
3	C	-	-	-
4	D	28	98 %	HP
Total		30	100%	

Information: H = haven't passed yet (Still not passed the standard minimum completeness criteria)

P = Passed (Has passed the standard minimum completeness criteria)

A = Excellent

B = Good

C = Fair

D = Poor

Based on the data above, it means that it is necessary to make efforts to improve learning for students in grade 9 D of SMP Negeri 2 Muntilan. The steps to improve learning are the treatment of learning in cycle 1 activities.

3. 2 Description of Learning Improvement Research Results Ciklus I

Table 4 below illustrates the results of the improvement scores in learning activities in cycle I In the development of grade 9 D student achievement results, there has been an increase. However, the increase still shows that there is no satisfactory treatment. In the sense that there are still many who have not exceeded the minimum standard of completeness criteria. The following is an explanation.

Table 4. Score of Cycle I Evaluation Results

No	Student's name	Cycle I Number of correct answers,	Total Score
1	Adi Nugroho	22	55
2	Agung Hendrawan Widiyanto	20	50

Increasing Student Learning Interest in the Subject "Indonesia in the Period of Independence" through the STAD Method (Student Teams Achievement Division)

3	Aisyah Nurjanah	24	60
4	Akhmad Syifa Fawaid	20	50
5	Alika Az zahra	18	45
6	Annisaa Nur Aeni	24	60
7	Ayu Wandira	28	70
8	Chalista Larasati Kusuma	22	55
9	Dewi Sri Bandiyah	24	60
10	Eisha Aulia Ramadani	22	55
11	Fadli Imam Muttaqin	32	80
12	Fardhan Yusuf Darmawan	23	57,5
13	Faris Rizq Ardiansyah	20	50
14	Febrianla Ahnaf Aufa Kurniawan	18	45
15	Kirana Ajwa Prameswari	19	47,5
16	Muhammad Raffi Pratama	25	62,5
17	Muhammad Rafi Khairi	23	51,7
18	Naf'an Fikri Nasoha	24	60
19	Nailun Ni'mah	25	62,5
20	Naura Kirania Hermawan	25	62,5
21	Niken Ayu Sekar Wigati	26	65
22	Putri Nurriil Lailatul Hidayah	24	60
23	Ragil Rizqi Yanuar	26	65
24	Reni Fadhilah Izzana	24	60
25	Satrio Cahyo Wicaksono	20	50
26	Silvi Nur Fadhila	20	50
27	Silvia Novita Ningrum	23	57,5
28	Siti 'Ainunna'Imah	26	65
29	Wulan Amelia	30	75
30	Yasmien Putri Hapsari	35	87,5
T o t a l			1774,2
Average Score			59,14

From the data above it can be seen that out of 30 students there were 4 students who scored more than 70 (exceeding the Minimum Completeness Criteria). The students who scored above 70 were Ayu Wandira, Fadli Imam Muttaqin, Wulan Amelia, and Yasmien Putri Hapsari.

Meanwhile, there were 12 students who scored 60 to 69. The twelve students are Aisyah Nurjanah, Annisaa Nu'Aini, Dewi Sri Bandiyah, Muhammad Raffi Pratama, Naf'an Fikri Nasoha, Nailun Ni'mah, Naura Kirania Hermawan, Niken Ayu Sekar Wigati, Putri Nurriil Lailatul Hidayah, Ragil Rizqi Yanuar, Reni Fadhilah Izzana, and Siti 'Ainunna'Imah.

There are 14 students who get scores below 60. The fourteen students are Adi Nugroho, Agung Hendrawan Widiyanto, Akhmad Syifa Fawaid, Alika Azzahra, Chalista Larasati Kusuma, Eisha Aulia Ramadani, Fardhan Yusuf Darmawan, Faris Rizq Ardiansyah, Febrianla Ahnaf Aufa Kurniawan, Kirana Ajwa Prameswari, Muhammad Rafi Khairi, Satrio Cahyo Wicaksono, Silvi Nur Fadhila, and Silvia Novita Ningrum.

However, from the data above, it can be concluded that by treating learning using the student teams achievement method, there has been a pretty good increase, even if the average is still below the minimum completeness criteria. For this reason, researchers make improvements to learning by improving themselves to see the advantages and at the same time the shortcomings that need to be corrected. One example of the seriousness of the students is still not optimal, there is still a lack of motivation which results in students still lacking enthusiasm to work even harder, study more intensively, and are serious in discussing and practicing speaking to convey their ideas.

To describe progress in a factual, clear and representative manner, the researcher seeks to display the development of learning achievement results by displaying tables. For more details can be seen in the following table 5.

Table 5. Recapitulation of Score Classification and Percentage of Social Science Score in Cycle 1

No	Classification	The Number of Students	Percentage	Completeness
1	A	4	13,3%	P
2	B	12	40%	P
3	C	6	20 %	HP
4	D	8	26,7 %	HP
T o t a l		30	100%	

Information: H = haven't passed yet (Still not passed the standard minimum completeness criteria)

P = Passed (Has passed the standard minimum completeness criteria)

Increasing Student Learning Interest in the Subject "Indonesia in the Period of Independence" through the STAD Method (Student Teams Achievement Division)

- A = Excellent
 B = Good
 C = Fair
 D = Poor

Starting from the data above, it means that researchers still need to make efforts to improve learning in class 9 D students of SMP Negeri 2 Muntilan. The steps to improve learning are the treatment of learning in cycle 2 activities.

3.2.1 Observation of Colleagues in Cycle 1

The next step is the role and function of colleagues in cycle 1 activities. The observation steps of colleagues 1 and colleagues 2 can be seen in table 6 and table 7. Figures table 6 and table 7 carefully observe the learning aspects provided by the research

Table 6. Peer Assessment 1 Observation Sheet on Teacher Performance in Cycle 1

Subjects : Social Science
 Class : 9D
 Day/Date : Thursday, 3 2022
 Observation Focus : Application of the Students Teams Achievement Division Method (STAD)

No	Aspects observed*)	Appearance **)		Coment***)
		Exist	Not axiest	
1	The Application of the student team achievement division method	√		Good
	-explain the main points of the material systematically	√		Good
	• Explain the tasks that must be done	√		Good
	• Giving students the opportunity to ask questions		√	Less
				Less
	• Doing group division	√		Good
	• Supervise group activities	√		Good
2	• Provide assistance to groups	√		Good
	The use of props and real objects for experiments	√		Good
	Use of props:		√	Less
3	• Ask for student comments		√	Less
	Students read the results of the experiment	√		Good
4	The teacher gives conclusions and strengthens the material	√		Good
5	The teacher distributes student worksheets	√		Good
6	Teachers do remedial		√	Less

*) Made detailed according to the needs of learning improvement

**) Put a √ sign

***) Provide an explanation of the suitability or non-compliance of the observed aspects with the established criteria

Magelang, October 25th 2022

Peer Assessment 1

Harisah Rachmawati,S.Pd.

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Table 7. Peer Assessment 2 Observation Sheet on Teacher Performance in Cycle 1

Subjects : Social Science
 Class : 9D
 Day/Date : Thursday, 3 2022
 Observation Focus : Application of the Students Teams Achievement Division Method (STAD)

No	Aspects observed*)	Appearance **)		Coment***)
		Exist	Not axiest	
1	The Application of the student team achievement division method	√		Good
	-explain the main points of the material systematically	√		Good
	• Explain the tasks that must be done	√		Good
	• Giving students the opportunity to ask questions		√	Less
	• Doing group division	√		Good
	• Supervise group activities	√		Good
	• Provide assistance to groups	√		Good
2	The use of props and real objects for experiments	√		Good

Increasing Student Learning Interest in the Subject "Indonesia in the Period of Independence" through the STAD Method (Student Teams Achievement Division)

	Use of props:	√	Less
	• Ask for student comments	√	Less
3	Students read the results of the experiment	√	Good
4	The teacher gives conclusions and strengthens the material	√	Good
5	The teacher distributes student worksheets	√	Good
6	Teachers do remedial	√	Less

*) Made detailed according to the needs of learning improvement

***) Put a √ sign

****) Provide an explanation of the suitability or non-compliance of the observed aspects with the established criteria

Magelang, October 25th 2022

Peer Assessment 2

Sugiwarni,S.Pd.Ek

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3.2.2 Reflection in Cycle 1

After researchers and colleagues carry out observations of the implementation of learning, the results of the observations can be reflected as follows:

- In making the *RPP (Rencana Pelaksanaan Pembelajaran/Learning Implementation Plan)*, the clarity of the problem has been well stated, and in accordance with the basic competencies.
- Basic competencies, indicators, objectives, and materials are appropriate.
- Assessment instruments also exist, and are equipped with worksheets.
- In the implementation of early learning, the teacher's readiness was seen both in spatial planning and preparation of learning tools, although they were not well organized.
- Apperception has been done.
- Children are enthusiastic in participating in learning.
- The snakes and ladders game activity ran smoothly but the results of the student evaluation still showed a low class average score of 59.14 and there were still 12 students who scored 60-69 (although sufficient but still in the minimum completeness criteria) and 14 students which is still below the value of 60. Therefore, this research still needs to be continued in the improvement of cycle II to improve student achievement.

3.3 Description of Learning Improvement Research Results Ciklus II

Table 8 below illustrates the results of the improvement scores in learning activities in cycle I. In the development of grade 9 D student achievement results, there has been an increase. However, the increase still shows that there is no satisfactory treatment. In the sense that there are still many who have not exceeded the minimum standard of completeness criteria. The following is an explanation.

Table 8. Score of Cycle II Evaluation Results

No	Student's name	Cycle II	
		Number of correct answers,	Total Score
1	Adi Nugroho	28	
2	Agung Hendrawan Widiyanto	29	5
3	Aisyah Nurjanah	29	5
4	Akhmad Syifa Fawaid	30	
5	Alika Az zahra	26	
6	Annisaa Nur Aeni	29	5
7	Ayu Wandira	28	
8	Chalista Larasati Kusuma	27	5
9	Dewi Sri Bandiyah	29	5
10	Eisha Aulia Ramadani	28	
11	Fadli Imam Muttaqin	35	5
12	Fardhan Yusuf Darmawan	31	5
13	Faris Rizq Ardiansyah	28	
14	Febrianla Ahnaf Aufa Kurniawan	26	
15	Kirana Ajwa Prameswari	29	5
16	Muhammad Raffi Pratama	29	5
17	Muhammad Rafi Khairi	28	
18	Naf'an Fikri Nasoha	28	

Increasing Student Learning Interest in the Subject "Indonesia in the Period of Independence" through the STAD Method (Student Teams Achievement Division)

19	Nailun Ni'mah	29	5
20	Naura Kirania Hermawan	34	
21	Niken Ayu Sekar Wigati	36	
22	Putri Nurriil Lailatul Hidayah	23	5
23	Ragil Rizqi Yanuar	23	5
24	Reni Fadhilah Izzana	28	
25	Satrio Cahyo Wicaksono	32	
26	Silvi Nur Fadhila	32	
27	Silvia Novita Ningrum	31	5
28	Siti 'Ainunna'Imah	33	5
29	Wulan Amelia	30	
30	Yasmien Putri Hapsari	36	
T o t a l			40
Average Score			666

From the data above, it can be concluded that on average all 9D class students at SMP Negeri 2 Muntilan have met the minimum completeness criteria. It turned out that out of 30 students there were still 3 students who did not meet the completeness criteria. The three students were 1) Alika Azzahra with 26 correct questions and a score of 65; 2) Chalista Larasati Kusuma by collecting the number of correct scores there were 27 and the final score was 67.5, while the last to get a score under the minimum completeness criteria was Febrianla Ahnaf Aufa Kurniawan. Febrianla Ahnaf Aufa Kurniawan got a total of 26 correct scores and a final score of 65. However, if we look at it in detail, it can be said that this research was successful. This can be seen from the significance of the increase in grades for all 9D grade students. Meanwhile, apart from these three students, all of them are above the Minimum Completeness Criteria.

3.3.1 Percentage Table

To describe progress in a factual, clear, and representative manner, which indicates that this research shows significant progress, can be seen in table 9. The following is table 9 which illustrates the progress of academic achievement which is quite spectacular.

Table 9. Recapitulation of Score Classification and Percentage of Social Science Score in Cycle II

No	Classification	The Number of Students	Percentage	Completeness
1	A	26	90%	P
2	B	-	-	-
3	C	4	10 %	HP
4	D	-	-	-
T o t a l		30	100%	

Information: H = haven't passed yet (Still not passed the standard minimum completeness criteria)

P = Passed (Has passed the standard minimum completeness criteria)

A = Excellent

B = Good

C = Fair

D = Poor

Based on the data in table 9 above, there were 27 students who could be said to have received good grades, while there were only 3 of the data above, meaning the researcher stated that efforts to improve learning in class 9 D students of SMP Negeri 2 Muntilan were declared successful. The next step is to maintain the value that has been achieved.

3.3.2 Observation of Colleagues in Cycle II

The next step is the role and function of colleagues in cycle 2 activities. Peer observation steps in cycle 2 can be seen in Tables 10 and 11. The tables describe peer observations in this classroom action research. An overview of the opinions of peer observers 1 and 2 in Cycle II can be seen in the following table.

Table 10. Peer Assessment 1 Observation Sheet on Teacher Performance in Cycle II

Subjects : Social Science

Class : 9D

Day/Date : Thursday, 3 2022

Observation Focus : Application of the Students Teams Achievement Division Method (STAD)

Increasing Student Learning Interest in the Subject "Indonesia in the Period of Independence" through the STAD Method (Student Teams Achievement Division)

No	Aspects observed*)	Appearance **)		Coment***)
		Exist	Not axiest	
1	The Application of the student team achievement division method	√		Good
	-explain the main points of the material systematically	√		Good
	• Explain the tasks that must be done	√		Good
	• Giving students the opportunity to ask questions	√		Less
				Less
	• Doing group division	√		Good
	• Supervise group activities	√		Good
	• Provide assistance to groups	√		Good
2	The use of props and real objects for experiments	√		Good
	Use of props:		√	Less
	• Ask for student comments	√		Less
3	Students read the results of the experiment	√		Good
4	The teacher gives conclusions and strengthens the material	√		Good
5	The teacher distributes student worksheets	√		Good
6	Teachers do remedial	√		Less

*) Made detailed according to the needs of learning improvement

**) Put a √ sign

***) Provide an explanation of the suitability or non-compliance of the observed aspects with the established criteria

Magelang, November 3th 2022

Peer Assessment 1

Harisah Rachmawati,S.Pd.

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Table 11. Peer Assesment 2 Observation Sheet on Teacher Performance in Cycle II

Subjects : Social Science

Class : 9D

Day/Date : Thursday, November 3th 2022

Observation Focus : Application of the Students Teams Achievement Division Method (STAD)

No	Aspects observed*)	Appearance **)		Coment***)
		Exist	Not axiest	
1	The Application of the student team achievement division method	√		Good
	-explain the main points of the material systematically	√		Good
	• Explain the tasks that must be done	√		Good
	• Giving students the opportunity to ask questions		√	Less
	• Doing group division	√		Good
	• Supervise group activities	√		Good
	• Provide assistance to groups	√		Good
2	The use of props and real objects for experiments	√		Good
	Use of props:		√	Less
	• Ask for student comments	√		Less
3	Students read the results of the experiment	√		Good
4	The teacher gives conclusions and strengthens the material	√		Good
5	The teacher distributes student worksheets	√		Good
6	Teachers do remedial	√		Less

*) Made detailed according to the needs of learning improvement

**) Put a √ sign

***) Provide an explanation of the suitability or non-compliance of the observed aspects with the established criteria

Magelang, October 25th 2022

Peer Assessment 2

Sugiwarni,S.Pd.Ek

NIP 19631023 198412 2 003

3.3.3 Reflection in Cycle II

After observing and discussing with colleagues, the reflections on cycle II are:

a. RPP (*Rencana Pelaksanaan Pembelajaran/learning implementation plan*) and learning implementation are more effective and

Increasing Student Learning Interest in the Subject "Indonesia in the Period of Independence" through the STAD Method (Student Teams Achievement Division)

better than cycle I.

b. Students are more active in learning activities.

c. Students' ability to understand the material and conduct experiments on the subject of objects and their properties has increased as evidenced by the increased evaluation results. It can be seen from the class average score that has increased and all students can get a complete score on the evaluation results.

Based on some of the data above, the researcher considers that learning on this subject has been successful and does not need to be continued in the next cycle. This can be seen and proven from the results through the increase in student learning achievement seen from the development of the pre-cycle, cycle I and cycle II. From the learning improvements carried out by researchers in Cycle II there was a significant increase in student learning outcomes. None of the students experienced a decrease in grades. However, there are still three students who are still under the KKM (Kriteria Ketuntasan Minimal/ Minimum Completion Criteria, such as: 1) Alika Azzahra (pre-cycle score of 27.5; cycle I score of 45, and in cycle II she received a score of 65); 2) Chalista Larasati Kusuma (pre-cycle score of 30, cycle I got a score of 55, and cycle II increased to 87.5); 3) Febrianla Ahnaf Aufa Kurniawan (pre-cycle score of 27.5, cycle I got a score of 45, and value in cycle II earned 65). However, vulgarly all students experienced an increase in grades. Only in the overview of Cycle I and Cycle II were there still a number of students whose grades remained (did not increase) but had exceeded the Minimum Mastery Criteria. The two students who did not experience an increase in achievement in cycle I and Cycle II were Wulan Wadira (cycle I earned 70 and cycle II was the same, namely 70 too); Meanwhile, another student whose score was the same was Wuolan Amelia (cycle I got 75, and in cycle II she also got 75).

From the statement above it can be concluded that learning using the students teams achievement division method can be said to be successful. This means that significantly, all students experienced a significant (significant) increase. Next is the presentation of values in Pre-cycle, Cycle I, and Cycle II. An overview of this increase in value is presented in table 12. The following is the explanation

Table 12. Data on Social Science Scores from Pre-cycle, Cycle I, and Cycle II for class 9 D of SMP Negeri 2 Muntilan, Magelang

NO.	Student's name	Score			Information	
		Pre-cycle	Cycle I	Cycle II	P	HP
1	Adi Nugroho	35	55	70	P	-
2	Agung Hendrawan Widiyanto	37,5	50	72,5	P	-
3	Aisyah Nurjanah	40	60	72,5	P	-
4	Akhmad Syifa Fawaid	35	50	75	P	-
5	Alika Az zahra	27,5	45	65	-	HP
6	Annisaa Nur Aeni	30	60	72,5	P	-
7	Ayu Wandira	37,5	70	70	P	-
8	Chalista Larasati Kusuma	30	55	67,5	-	HP
9	Dewi Sri Bandiyah	45	60	72,5	P	-
10	Eisha Aulia Ramadani	47,5	55	70	P	-
11	Fadli Imam Muttaqin	75	80	87,5	P	-
12	Fardhan Yusuf Darmawan	50	57,5	77,5	P	-
13	Faris Rizq Ardiansyah	50	50	70	P	-
14	Febrianla Ahnaf Aufa Kurniawan	27,5	45	65	-	HP
15	Kirana Ajwa Prameswari	37,5	47,5	72,5	P	-
16	Muhammad Raffi Pratama	35	62,5	72,5	P	-
17	Muhammad Rafi Khairi	50	51,7	70	P	-
18	Naf'an Fikri Nasoha	35	60	70	P	-
19	Nailun Ni'mah	42,5	62,5	72,5	P	-
20	Naura Kirania Hermawan	32,5	62,5	85	P	-
21	Niken Ayu Sekar Wigati	50	65	90	P	-
22	Putri Nuril Lailatul Hidayah	42,5	60	72,5	P	-
23	Ragil Rizqi Yanuar	52,5	65	72,5	P	-
24	Reni Fadhilah Izzana	47,5	60	70	P	-
25	Satrio Cahyo Wicaksono	27,5	50	80	P	-
26	Silvi Nur Fadhila	22,5	50	80	P	-
27	Silvia Novita Ningrum	52,5	57,5	77,5	P	-
28	Siti 'Ainunna'Imah	52,5	65	82,5	P	-
29	Wulan Amelia	47,5	75	75	P	-
30	Yasmien Putri Hapsari	77,5	87,5	90	P	-
T o t a l		1272,5	1774,2	2240		
Average Score		42,416	59,14	74,3		

Increasing Student Learning Interest in the Subject "Indonesia in the Period of Independence" through the STAD Method (Student Teams Achievement Division)

Information:

H = haven't passed yet (Still not passed the standard minimum completeness criteria)

P = Passed (Has passed the standard minimum completeness criteria)

A = Excellent

B = Good

C = Fair

D = Poor

Furthermore, to find out the percentage weight of the value difference can be seen in table number 13. Table number 13 illustrates a gradation comparison of the acquisition of values in pre-cycle, cycle I, and cycle II. From the results of the children in terms of percentages, it was clear that all of them had significant children. Below is a description of the recapitulation of the grouping of values and percentages from before the improvement was made, then learning improvement, the process of which was measured from cycle I and cycle II.

Table 13. Recapitulation of grouping scores and percentages from before improvement, Cycle I, Cycle II, Social Science

No	Score	Pre-cycle The number of student	Percentage	Cycle I The number of student	Percentage	Cycle II The number of student	Percentage
1	A	0	0 %	1	3,333 %	7	23,333 %
2	B	2	6,666%	3	10 %	23	76,666 %
3	C	11	36,666 %	26	86,666 %	0	0 %
4	D	17	56,666 %	0	0 %	0	0 %
Total		30	100 %	20	100 %	20	100 %

3.4 Discussion of Learning Improvement Research Results

From the learning that has been done by researchers at the pre-cycle stage there have been no satisfactory results. There were only 2 students who completely met the KKM standard above 70. The two students were named Fadli Imam Muttqin with a score of 75 and the second was Yasmien Putri Hapsari with a score of 77.5. These two students, although they scored above 70, were still classified as B (good, but not very satisfying). This was caused by several things, including the method used by the teacher was not appropriate, not supported by adequate teaching aids, and students were not involved actively in learning.

By improving learning in cycle I that applies the student teams achievement division method, assisted by teaching aids and student worksheets (LKS), students have experienced pretty good grades. However, the results of the achievements in cycle I were still not satisfactory, in the sense that they did not meet the expectations of the researchers. The results of the first cycle of students who scored above the KKM increased even though it was not significant. Why? Because only 4 students experienced an increase above the Minimum Completeness Criteria. The four students are 1) Ayu Wandira (with a score of 70); 2) Fadli Imam Muttqin (pre-cycle score of 80); 3) Wulan Amelia (score 75); and 4) Yasmien Putri Hapsari 87.5). That means that only 45% of students have reached the KKM, there are still 55% who have not reached the KKM because the teacher does not explain the material concept of energy and influence in everyday life, the teacher does not set an example in playing the snakes and ladders game so there are still students who are confused. in carrying out the game of snakes and ladders, and the deficiencies were corrected in the improvement of cycle II learning.

After learning improvements were held in Cycle II with the student achievement division and worksheet methods, students' understanding of the historical understanding of the Indonesian Independence Period sub-topics in everyday life increased. It is shown by the number of students who get scores above the KKM to 30 children or 100% so that learning outcomes can reach the target. The following below is a diagram of the increase in learning improvement results starting from pre-cycle, Cycle I, Cycle II

Figure 1. Diagram of Comparison of Improved Learning Results from Pre-Cycle, Cycle I, and Cycle II

Increasing Student Learning Interest in the Subject "Indonesia in the Period of Independence" through the STAD Method (Student Teams Achievement Division)

If the learning outcomes expressed in percentages are as follows.

Percentage before repair : 1) Students who score 81-100 are 0 students = 0 %; 2) Students who score 61 - 80 are 4 students = 6.666 %; 3) Students who score 41 - 60 are 3 students = 36.666 %; 4) Students who score less than 40 = 56.666 %. Percentage of improvement in Cycle I: 1) Students who score 81-100 are 0 students = 3.333 %; 2) Students who score 61 - 80 are 4 students = 10%; 3) Students who score 41 - 60 are 3 students = 86.666 %; 4) Students who score less than 40 = 0 %. Percentage of improvement in Cycle II: 1) Students who score 81-100 are 0 students = 23.333 %; 2) Students who score 61 - 80 are 4 students = 76.666 %; 3) Students who score 41 - 60 are 3 students = 0%; 4) Students who score less than 40 = 0 %.

Based on these value data, it can be seen clearly that in Cycle I, there was an increase in learning outcomes which on average rose in Cycle I by an average of 20.57% and in Cycle II by an average of 42.29%. So, it can also be concluded that through the use of the students teams achievement division method, student achievement in Social Studies learning, the subject matter of Indonesia Massa Kemerdekaan, increased significantly. Furthermore, an overview of the development of the increase can be seen in the diagram below. This diagram depicts in detail from Cycle I and Cycle II at the same time.

Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that the application of the method students teams achievement division declared successful. All students experience increase in value both in the stages of Cycle I and Cycle II. There are still three students who have not reached the KKM (Minimum Completeness Criteria), but in the third gradation students can be said to have increased significantly. For more he explained, the process of increasing the development of achievement of class 9D students of SMP Negeri 2 Muntilan can be seen in the graphic image below.

Figure 2. Graph comparison between Pre-cycle, Cycle I and Cycle II scores

IV. CONCLUSION

With the completion of this learning improvement activity, based on the implementation stages starting from Pre-cycle, Cycle I to Cycle II, the researcher can draw a conclusion that:

- The results of improving learning using the study teams achievement division method in Cycle I (first) the results obtained were an average of 59.14. Halk has experienced an increase of 20.57% %. This is not optimal because not all students can understand the material well so there are still some students who do not understand the teacher's explanation and have not mastered the game activities (implementation of the students teams achievement division method) that are being carried out.
- In cycle II the increase in learning outcomes is very good. This can be seen from the results of the scores obtained by students on average 77.333 with a completeness percentage of 100%. Thus it can be concluded that this increase is very good. This score was obtained because students were able to answer questions posed by the teacher properly and correctly, students had optimally understood the student teams achievement division method clearly, and cooperation in groups had begun to be fostered.
- By providing subject matter through the optimal use of the student achievement division method, this can stimulate creativity, collaboration, and student curiosity high enough so that the classroom atmosphere is conducive, and learning objectives can be achieved effectively, creating an active learning atmosphere. Innovative, Creative, Effective, Fun, Enthusiastic, Optimistic, Compact, Happy, and Great (PAIKEM SEMOK GEMBROT).

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